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REVIEW ARTICLE

Diagnosis and Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease and Parkinson's Disease with Resonance Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Parkinson Disease (PD) is a degenerative disease of the extrapyramidal motor system. The formations of the midbrain are affected and are expressed in 1. Tremor, 2. Hypokinesia, 3. Muscle rigidity, 4. Postural instability. Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a progressive form of senile dementia, leading to a complete loss of cognitive abilities, developing mainly after 60-65 years of age. With these diseases, a large number of brain structures degenerate, including demyelinating brain processes. Both diseases are considered incurable. This article presents materials for the effective treatment of diseases by the method of resonance medicine - mainly the resonance of creation. With the help of the resonance of creation, the degenerated structures of the brain are restored. Until now, no methods have been known to restore dead brain cells. This review aims to present materials on the effective treatment (cure) of these diseases. For the treatment, the resonance therapy method was used, which has been known for at least 25 years and which has been modified in our work since 2016. The essence of our modification was that the author began to use 1. Not only low (previously known), but also high potencies of resonant drugs. 2. We have created a direction in resonance therapy, which is called "resonance of creation." So far, only the direction known as "resonance of destruction" is known, with the help of which oncological tissues, infectious processes, cysts, stones, etc. are treated - destroyed. With the help of the resonance of creation, various biological structures that have undergone degeneration and death are restored - the myelin sheath of the nerves in multiple sclerosis, nerve cells in Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease, etc. With the help of the resonance of creation, the beta cells of the tail of the pancreas are restored in type 1 diabetes, and restoration of the lymphoid system in autoimmune diseases. For the treatment of PD and AD, appropriate preparations are prepared from the tested organopreparations. They are recorded on sugar grains in the potency that is necessary for treatment and resonant treatment of patients is carried out. Treatment of all tested brain structures showed that the patient responds to this treatment quite adequately. In the process of treatment, the "insular cortex" was the first to stop testing, then the "basal nucleus". As the testability of these brain structures decreased, the patient reported that his condition became significantly better, not only in terms of short-term memory recovery, but also in other indicators.

In patients with moderate dementia, in the first weeks of treatment, organ preparations, the "insular cortex", "basal nucleus", "temporal lobe", "isocortex" and those that are characteristic of Parkinson's disease - "lenticular nucleus", "paranigra dopamine nuclei of the middle brain", "roof of the midbrain". Subsequently, the hippocampus, the piriform lobe, the insular field, and the hippocampal pre-basement were no longer tested. At the same time, the reports of the patients' relatives changed: "Our patient began to cry less, be less offended by us and began to recognize loved ones more often - children, grandchildren. Another very important thing is that it has become easier to get up from a chair. Before starting treatment, getting up from a chair was a difficult and lengthy process for her. She became less touchy, became less likely to incontinence. Treatment is carried out until the complete loss of AD symptoms. It has been established that in Alzheimer's disease, the restoration of degenerated formations - the hippocampus, neocortex, amygdala, basal nucleus, isocortex, the pre-foundation of the hippocampus, the insular cortex, the brain septum, the temporal lobe, the parietal lobe, the paralimbic cortex, the piriform lobe led to the restoration these degenerated masses and effective clinical improvement in patients with Alzheimer's disease. The above indicates the effective treatment of PD and AD by the method of resonance of creation.

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Alzheimer's Disease (AD)

Alzheimer's disease is a progressive form of senile dementia, leading to a complete loss of cognitive abilities, developing mainly after 60–65 years of age. It is clinically manifested by a gradual and constantly progressive disorder of cognitive abilities: attention, memory, speech, praxis, gnosis, psychomotor coordination, orientation and thinking [1,2].

Dementia of the Alzheimer's type is characterized by a subtle and prolonged onset, steady progression without periods of improvement. The main substrate of the disease are disorders of higher nervous functions.

In Alzheimer's disease, the following brain structures are affected: amygdala, nucleus basalis, insular cortex, cerebral septum, hippocampus, neocortex, temporal lobe, parietal lobe, isocortex, piriformis lobe, insular field, hippocampal pre-basement, paralimbic cortex.

Parkinson's Disease (PD)

Clinical manifestations of PD are expressed in 1. Tremor, 2. Hypokinesia, 3. Muscle rigidity, 4. Postural instability. In the hyperkinetic form of PD, there is a decrease in the tone of skeletal muscles [3,4].

PD is a degenerative disease of the extrapyramidal motor system. The formations of the midbrain are affected – the red nucleus, the substantia nigra, the reticular formation, the quadrigemina plate, the amygdala (limbic system). In the hyperkinetic form of PD, the striopallid system, the caudate and lenticular nuclei, is involved in the pathological process.

PD is a classic example of a degenerative disease. In the affected structures, the number of neurons sharply decreases, and, as a result, there is a decrease in the content of dopamine in them.

In allopathic medicine, the treatment of the disease is carried out according to the principle of replacement therapy. Patients take dopamine drugs. It is clear that such a principle of therapy cannot lead to a cure for PD.

In PD, those brain structures that are involved in the pathological process in Alzheimer's Disease (AD) are also tested, namely: amygdala, nucleus basalis, insular cortex, brain septum, hippocampus, neocortex, temporal lobe of the brain, parietal lobe of the brain, isocortex, piriformis share, islet field. At the same time, those features of the disease that are characteristic of AD (with early and moderate dementia) are revealed.

Treatment of PD and AD

Parkinson disease

Most patients with Parkinson's disease receive medication to relieve the symptoms of the disease. These

drugs work by stimulating the remaining cells in the substantia nigra to produce more dopamine (Levodopa) or by inhibiting some of the acetylcholines produced (anticholinergics).

If Parkinson's disease progresses, Levodopa is used for symptomatic treatment. This is a drug with an active substance that is a precursor of dopamine. It turns into dopamine in peripheral tissues and weakens most of the symptoms of the disease, corrects well-being. The effect on the work of the central nervous system is limited, so Levodopa is combined with other drugs.

Psychiatrists and neurologists in most cases use the following groups of medications:

Cholinesterase inhibitors. These drugs are used for many degenerative diseases. They prevent the destruction of acetylcholine. It promotes the conduction of nerve signals. With the restoration of this signal, memory is restored in patients, and attention improves.

NMDA receptor antagonists. They are prescribed to normalize the patient's mental activity. Taking pills normalizes concentration and attention.

Antipsychotics – able to remove such symptoms of the disease as aggression, delusions and hallucinations. The appointment of this drug must be agreed with a psychiatrist. It is important to choose the right dosage.

Tranquilizers. Appointed to combat anxiety, fear, panic attacks.

Normotimics – necessary for the patient to normalize mood. They are prescribed to patients who have mental disorders. They are prescribed when the disease has changed the character of the patient. Able to remove the manifestation of aggression,

Antidepressants. Helps fight depression. Appointed by a medical specialist.

Alzheimer's disease

According to the 2010 European Federation of Neurologic Societies (EFNS) clinical guidelines, Cholinesterase Inhibitors (CEI), anticholinergic agents, and monoclonal antibody preparations (adukanumab and zumab) have proven efficacy, which allow the removal of beta-amyloid aggregates from tissue brain, thereby stabilizing the cognitive functions of patients. The clinical efficacy of drugs of other classes – neurotrophic, anti-amyloid (immunotherapy and secretase inhibitors), anti-inflammatory and nootropic drugs (for example, piracetam and nicergoline), mitochondriotropic drugs and antioxidants, statins, selegiline, pentoxifylline – remains unproven to date. Data on the effectiveness of Ginkgo biloba (EGb) and cerebrolysin are contradictory, which gives reason to use these drugs when it is impossible to undergo basic treatment. For mild to moderate AD,

methods of cognitive stimulation and rehabilitation can be used. Unfortunately, all the proposed most modern methods cannot cure PD and AD. These two diseases remain incurable diseases.

Since this article focuses on the diagnosis and treatment of these two diseases using resonance medicine, this section is preceded by a brief introduction to what is called "resonance".

From a technical point of view, resonance is a phenomenon of the response of an oscillatory system to an external influence. When the periods of exposure and the response of the system coincide, a resonance occurs - a sharp increase in the amplitude of the oscillations under consideration.

Resonance was discovered by Galelei G [5]. The resonance can be most clearly described as follows. A platoon of soldiers approaches a wooden bridge and the officer gives the command to go out of step because if a platoon of soldiers crosses the wooden bridge in step, the bridge may collapse from resonance. The vibrations of the bridge will coincide with the vibrations of the marching soldiers, a resonance will arise, from which the bridge will collapse.

In this review, the role of the bridge is "played" by the disease, and the role of marching soldiers is "performed" by the therapeutic effect. The commander of the soldiers did not want the bridge to collapse due to possible resonance. The doctor, by contrast, absolutely needs a resonance to destroy the disease.

Resonance methods for studying matter have found wide application in physics, chemistry, biology, and medicine. For example, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR).

At the end of the 20th century, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) was developed on the basis of NMR. It is used to obtain images of the human brain, heart, and digestive tract organs. For the development of MRI in 2003, the American biophysicist Paul Lauterbur and his English colleague Peter Mansfield were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine.

In 1975, the German physician Frank Morell came to the quite logical conclusion that if a disease of the organs of the human body is inevitably accompanied by disturbances in their frequency rhythm, then the essence of treatment should be to suppress the "unhealthy" fluctuations that have arisen and restore normal ones.

The vegetative resonance test - VRT, originally proposed in 1991 by the German scientist Schimmel G [6], allows one-point examination. Testing only one biologically active point makes it possible to assess the state of not only all organs and systems, but also their interconnections.

A device for resonance therapy based on a computer was created, which included both diagnostic and therapeutic

parts. In a modern device for resonance therapy there is a large selector with diagnostic (they are also therapeutic) markers, information copies of diseases, which are called "nosodes" when it comes to the disease and "organo-preparations" - information copies of healthy organs when the doctor deals with normal, not pathological organs or their parts. "Nosodes" are needed for the identification and treatment of diseases, and "organo-preparations" for testing perfectly healthy organs or parts of them. Nosodes are electronic markers about a disease and "organopreparations" - information markers about a healthy organ or part of it, recorded on a specific medium.

Each test drug exerts a wave effect on the patient. It is necessary to restore the spectral (frequency) harmony in the patient.

Original test preparations (unlike their informational copies) are material objects, i.e. specific substances with their own atomic and molecular structure. Movement is an essential property of matter. Everything moves: from galaxies, stars and planets to the smallest particles of matter resonance of destruction.

Diagnosis using destruction resonance

The use of destruction resonance has been taking place for more than two hundred years. The doctor creates such a relationship between the drug and the pathological process in the patient, in which the periods of exposure and the response of the system coincide and resonance occurs - a sharp increase in the amplitude of oscillations, resulting in the destruction of the pathological focus.

In the activities of a doctor who uses resonance therapy, a similar process takes place using modern technologies. First, a diagnosis is made. To do this, the nosode of the alleged disease is displayed on the screen of a computer connected to a device for resonance therapy and it is tested in a patient. If the nosode is "not tested", then there is no resonance and the arrow on the computer screen does not fall down in the middle of the screen. Therefore, the patient does not have the disease that is displayed by the nosode. In the same case, if the nosode is tested, there is a resonance between the patient and the test drug - the arrow on the computer screen falls and indicates that the patient has the disease, the name of which is the nosode. This is a diagnostic resonance, but not a therapeutic one. This is how resonance diagnostics is carried out in resonance therapy.

Healing with resonance of destruction

To treat a detected disease, the doctor must destroy either the tumor or the infectious process with the help of resonance, and for this it is necessary to potentiate the nosode detected in the patient, i.e. to find that potency of the nosode that will cause resonance with the pathological process in the patient and destroy the disease, in other

words, therapeutic resonance is needed. To do this, find that potency of the nosode (usually high), which leads to the fact that when testing this nosode in a patient, the arrow stops falling. Such a potency of the nosode leads to a resonant destruction of the structures of the disease. In other words, the informational content of the nosode in a certain potency is used for the resonant destruction of the structure of the disease, namely the treatment of the disease found. The doctor records the informational content of the potentiated nosode on a sugar grain and the patient takes this sugar grain and is thus treated, i.e. there is a resonant destruction of the structure of the disease.

The use of only extremely low potencies for the treatment of various diseases of resonance therapy did not allow and does not allow to effectively treat many diseases, including oncological diseases, many infectious diseases, etc. In other words, there has been a crisis for many years in resonance therapy. This can be seen in the materials of the annual scientific conferences on resonance therapy [7].

Since 2016, materials have been published on the use of high potency drugs for treatment [8-16]. It was found that drugs of high and ultra-high potencies do not cause any side effects, including toxic effects on sick and healthy people. But high potency preparations proved to be exceptionally effective in the treatment of severe and extremely severe diseases such as cancer, infectious diseases, including HIV, stones and cysts in organs [8-16]. In particular, metastatic forms of oncology are effectively treated. It has been established that all those forms of oncological diseases that are in the selector of the device for resonance therapy are effectively treated with drugs of high and ultra-high potencies.

Treatment of patients with drugs of high potency nosodes was not an end in itself. This method was found in medical practice.

In our previous works [14-16] and in monographs [10-15] considered two options for using resonance in medicine - the resonance of destruction and the resonance of creation. Resonance has been used for many years in the treatment of various diseases [16]. In this paper, we will consider the possibilities of effective treatment of diabetes and autoimmune diseases using the methods resonance of creation. In the diagnosis and treatment of resonance therapy, the so-called "nosodes" are used - wave copies of various diseases, including oncological ones, and "organopreparations" - wave copies of normally functioning organs. A feature of the use of nosodes and organopreparations in our work was that we used not only low potencies of nosodes and organopreparations, but also high ones [8-16], while in previous works we used only low potencies of nosodes and organopreparations [8-16].

So, resonance medicine includes resonance diagnostics

and resonance therapy. The treatment of patients in which the destruction of the structure of the disease occurs, for example, oncology, is called "destruction resonance".

Resonance of Creation

Since 2016, materials have been published on the use of the second direction of therapeutic resonance - the "resonance of creation" [8-16]. Resonance can not only destroy, for example, diseases, but also create lost biological structures. This made it possible to treat degenerative diseases.

We have not been able to find in the scientific literature an idea that resonance can be not only a "resonance of destruction", but also a "resonance of creation". This is obviously due to the fact that it is not easy to imagine how the coincidence of frequencies leads to a response that is not destructive, but creative. In this review, we have presented illustrations of how resonance can be not only destructive, but also constructive, in particular for the treatment of degenerative diseases.

In the treatment with the resonance of destruction, the nosodes of diseases were used, from which preparations were prepared in the high potency. This principle has not been effective for the treatment of degenerative diseases. The creation and formation of the principle of "resonance of creation" became possible only as a result of the fact that not nosodes were used for treatment, but organopreparation of high potency. Without high potency organopreparations, it is impossible to imagine the use of this principle.

This review presents materials related to the treatment of degenerative diseases. This means that treatment is nothing but the process of restoring organs or organ systems that have undergone changes as a result of diseases or as a result of the senile degenerative process.

Degenerative diseases can also be congenital. It is clear that a significant part of congenital diseases is the result of underdevelopment of an organ or organ system.

In practice, most often after a disease, for example, inflammation or as a result of the senile process, the level of health of the organ drops until it is destroyed. Such an organ requires restoration (rehabilitation). The resonance of creation makes it possible to restore an organ or part of it.

Organopreparations are wave preparations (wave copies) of healthy organs or their parts. Nosodes are wave preparations of the disease.

There are various organopreparations in the selectors of hardware and software complexes for resonance therapy. For the restoration and rehabilitation of organs, we used organopreparations in high potency.

Diagnosis of the Degenerative Process by the Method

Vegetative resonance test

When a patient is tested for an organ destroyed by a tumor, degenerative processes, or inflammation, it ceases to be tested as normal. In other words, it is tested as problematic. Those on the computer screen, an arrow falls in the middle of the screen, which indicates that the organopreparation was found correctly. There is a resonance between the organopreparation and the patient. This is a diagnostic resonance, but not a therapeutic one.

Treatment of the degenerative process with the resonance method creation

We find that potency of the organopreparation, which leads to resonance with the affected organ, namely, the cessation of testing this organ or part of the organ as problematic. At the same time, the drop of the arrow on the computer screen stops. This is a therapeutic resonance, but not a diagnostic one. The doctor prepares for the patient preparations of healthy organs in high potency, writes them down on sugar grains, which the patient takes.

Resonance diagnosis of alzheimer's disease

In the device selector, we find the following organopreparations of degenerated brain formations in AD, necessary for treatment: amygdala, nucleus basalis, insular cortex, brain septum, hippocampus, neocortex, temporal lobe, parietal lobe, isocortex, piriformis lobe, insular field, hippocampal pre-basement, paralimbic region of the cortex. All of these structures are tested in patients, i.e. the arrow falls when testing the listed organ preparations in patients. The nosode is also tested - Amyloid or Amyloidosis, brain plaques (neurotic plaques), prions. We are testing atherosclerosis as an extremely important cause of AD. In AD, as a rule, those structures are tested that are also tested in Parkinson's disease - the black medulla, the reticular formation, the quadrigeminal plate, etc., which are included in the treatment.

It is important to pay attention to the fact that the identification by testing of the given brain structures (they are tested) is necessary for the diagnosis of AD. Cases have been noted when a doctor does not detect any clinical symptoms of BA, but tests the given configuration of brain structures on the device. A similar situation was noted when a doctor tests a different configuration of brain structures characteristic of Parkinson's disease even in the period of the disease, when there are no clinical manifestations of the disease. In this, one can see very great possibilities of resonance diagnostics - a vegetative-resonance test [8-16].

Treatment of BA by the method of resonance of creation

After testing, resonance diagnostics, all of the listed organ preparations, treatment is carried out using the resonance method of creating BA. Corresponding preparations are prepared from the tested organopreparations. They are recorded on sugar grains in the potency that is necessary for treatment and resonant treatment of patients is carried out.

Treatment of patients with early and moderate dementia

Treatment of all tested brain structures showed that the patient responds to this treatment quite adequately. In the process of treatment, the "insular cortex" was the first to stop testing, then the "basal nucleus". As the testability of these brain structures decreased, the patient reported that his condition became significantly better, not only in terms of short-term memory recovery, but also in other indicators.

In patients with moderate dementia, in the first weeks of treatment, organopreparations, the "insular cortex", "basal nucleus", "temporal lobe", "isocortex" and those that are characteristic of Parkinson's disease - "lenticular nucleus", "paranigra dopamine nuclei of the middle brain", "roof of the midbrain".

Subsequently, the hippocampus, the piriform lobe, the insular field, and the hippocampal pre-basement were no longer tested. At the same time, the reports of the patients' relatives changed: "Our patient began to cry less, be less offended by us and began to recognize loved ones more often - children, grandchildren. Another very important thing is that it has become easier to get up from a chair. Before starting treatment, getting up from a chair was a difficult and lengthy process for her. She became less touchy, became less likely to incontinence. Treatment is carried out until the complete loss of symptoms of asthma.

Diagnosis and treatment of demyelination in patients with Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease

It has been shown that the process of demyelination and multiple sclerosis in general can be effectively treated (cured) by the resonance of creation [8-13].

It has been established that demyelination of nerve formations is essential in the pathogenesis of diseases of the nervous system. It has been established that in Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease there is a significant demyelination of nerve structures. How does this circumstance affect the therapeutic process? Patients with Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease were tested for the presence of demyelination in them, especially those structures that are associated with the main symptoms

of these diseases. It has been established that in these two diseases there is a distinct demyelination not only of those structures that are not directly related to the symptoms of these diseases, but also of those that are directly related to the manifestation of these two diseases. This is of great importance especially for the therapeutic process. It has been established that targeted treatment of degeneration in Parkinson's disease only, for example, the black medullary substance of the midbrain, the red nucleus, the lenticular nucleus, the roof of the midbrain, certainly leads to the restoration of these degenerated formations and a significant clinical improvement in the condition of these patients. It has also been established that in Alzheimer's disease, the restoration of degenerated formations - the hippocampus, neocortex, amygdala, basal nucleus, isocortex, the pre-foundation of the hippocampus, insular cortex, brain septum, temporal lobe, parietal lobe, paralimbic cortex, piriformis led to the restoration of these degenerated formations and effective clinical improvement in patients with Alzheimer's disease. However, it was often necessary to conduct repeated courses of restoration of brain structures due to the fact that there were relapses of degeneration and relapses of restoration of the symptom complexes of these diseases.

Naturally, the question arose to what extent effective treatment of demyelination of these formations can improve the condition of patients with Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease, stop or reduce the frequency of relapses of the degeneration process? Preliminary testing of the state of the nervous structures for the presence of a demyelination process in them indicated that these patients had a completely distinct process of demyelination, namely, local multiple sclerosis. That is why complex therapy was carried out, the treatment of these diseases not only of formations that have undergone degeneration, but also of local multiple sclerosis or demyelination. The potency of the myelin organo- preparation (myelin sheath) was selected for patients, which corresponded to the level of their demyelination and was prescribed to patients with both Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease.

The results of the work showed that the inclusion of demyelination in the therapeutic process of treatment led to a significant improvement in the state of the nervous system in these patients - a significant decrease in the recurrence of degeneration and thereby prolonging the process of effective treatment. The results of this work indicate that additional treatment of the demyelinating process led to a qualitative improvement in the state of the nervous system compared to what took place without the inclusion of treatment for the demyelinating process. The process of restoring the nervous system not only accelerated sharply, but also increased the time of absence of recurrence of the disease.

The above indicates the effective treatment of PD and AD by the method of resonance of creation [8-13].

Thus, the article shows effective diagnosis and treatment of both Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. It follows from the above that the materials of this review article meet the three principles of evidence-based medicine - scientific character (resonance - scientific non-direction), efficiency and safety.

Conclusion

This article presents materials for the effective treatment of diseases by the method of resonance medicine - mainly the resonance of creation. With the help of the resonance of creation, the degenerated structures of the brain are restored. This review aims to present materials on the effective treatment (cure) of Alzheimer disease and Parkinson disease. For the treatment, the resonance therapy method was used, which has been known for at least 25 years and which has been modified in our work since 2016. The essence of our modification was that the author began to use 1. Not only low (previously known), but also high potencies of resonant drugs. 2. We have created a direction in resonance therapy, which is called "resonance of creation." So far, only the direction known as "resonance of destruction" is known, with the help of which oncological tissues, infectious processes, cysts, stones, etc. are treated - destroyed. With the help of the resonance of creation, various biological structures that have undergone degeneration and death are restored - the myelin sheath of the nerves in multiple sclerosis, nerve cells in Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease, etc. With the help of the resonance of creation, the beta cells of the tail of the pancreas are restored in type 1 diabetes, and restoration of the lymphoid system in autoimmune diseases. For the treatment of PD and AD, appropriate preparations are prepared from the tested organopreparations. They are recorded on sugar grains in the potency that is necessary for treatment and resonant treatment of patients is carried out. Treatment of all tested brain structures showed that the patient responds to this treatment quite adequately. In the process of treatment, the "insular cortex" was the first to stop testing, then the "basal nucleus". As the testability of these brain structures decreased, the patient reported that his condition became significantly better, not only in terms of short-term memory recovery, but also in other indicators.

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